

Ecosystem and Landuse Policy Group (ELPEG) Bulletin – May 2024

Introduction

Welcome to this, our fourth ELPEG bulletin of the 2022-2027 RESAS strategic research programme. The aim of this bulletin is to provide policy makers with updates on the research on biodiversity that is happening within the strategic research programme. The bulletin will cover work from Topic D4 (Biodiversity) and the biodiversity elements within the air pollution Topic (D1).

For this bulletin we have updated the one-page summaries of the seven projects within the biodiversity topic and the one project within the air pollution topic that covers the impacts of pollution on biodiversity.

In addition, we have section provided by Jack Bloodworth, (Principal Science Adviser (Chemicals, Biodiversity), Rural & Environmental Science and Analytical Services) providing a policy update for the areas of policy relevant to ELPEG.

We welcome your feedback on this bulletin and if you have comments please do either provide them at the ELPEG meeting or contact Ruth.Mitchell@hutton.ac.uk

Contents

- [Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital](#)
- [Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems](#)
- [Nature and People](#)
- [Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers](#)
- [Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring](#)
- [Habitat management and restoration](#)
- [Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future](#)
- [Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health](#)
- [Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands](#)
- [Policy update](#)

Introduction to Theme D and how to find out more about the work on Soils, Water and Natural Capital

Theme D - Natural Resources is one of five themes in the Strategic Research Programme. The others are A Plant and Animal Health, B Sustainable Food System and Supply, C Human impacts on the Environment and E Rural Futures.

Within Theme D there are five Topics D1 Air Quality, D2 Water (inc Flooding), D3 Soils, D4 Biodiversity, D5 Natural Capital. ELPEG and ELSEG will largely focus on D4 Biodiversity and the biodiversity work in D1 Air Quality.

Each Topic has their own mechanisms for engagement with policy and with stakeholders:

D1 – Air pollution

The project on ammonia emissions is working specifically with the CAFS2 (Cleaner Air for Scotland Strategy) Agriculture and Environment Working Group (AEWG) and the project on particulates with the CAFS2 Domestic Emissions Working Group (DEWG). The project on air pollution and biodiversity is engaging with ELPEG and ELSEG. Contact Andrea.Britton@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D2 - Water (inc Flooding)

This Topic has established an engagement group with SG policy (teams working on Water and Environment, Flooding, Water Industry team, Drinking Water Quality) and a wider engagement group (including NatureScot, SEPA, Councils, Scottish Water, NHS, land managers and communities). The project has two new webpages with information about ongoing work:

[Achieving multi-purpose nature-based solutions - James Hutton Institute](#)

[Emerging water futures - James Hutton Institute](#)

Contact Mark.Wilkinson@hutton.ac.uk for further details about work in any of the projects within the water topic.

D3 - Soils

A copy of the latest newsletter produced by this Topic "The Soil Sentinel" is attached. Contact Eric.Paterson@hutton.ac.uk or Kenneth.Loades@hutton.ac.uk for further details.

D5 - Natural Capital

Each project in the topic area has a different mix of key stakeholders. These include ONS, NatureScot, Defra, SEPA and the Office of the Chief Economic Advisor (OCEA), but also go beyond these, as a key rationale for working with natural capital is mainstreaming consideration of nature across sectors. A summary of the projects within this Topic was circulated with the October 22 ELPEG bulletin called "2022-27 D5 Natural Capital 6 x projects".

Please see the links below for details about the projects within the Natural Capital Topic:

- Bringing in Participatory Approaches to widen the scope of natural capital valuation (JHI-D5-1; Simone.Martino@hutton.ac.uk - note change in leadership)

<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/bringing-participatory-approaches-widen-scope-natural-capital-valuation> [link down at time of writing but due to be restored]

- Climate change impacts on Natural Capital (JHI-D5-2; Mike.Rivington@hutton.ac.uk)
<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/climate-change-impacts-natural-capital>
- Galvanising Change via Natural Capital (JHI-D5-3; Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk)
<https://www.hutton.ac.uk/research/projects/galvanising-change-natural-capital>
- Modelling the socio-economic, greenhouse gas and natural capital impacts of land use policy and opportunities (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk) <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/modelling-the-socio-economic-greenhouse-gas-and-natural-capital-impacts-of-land%20use-policy-and-opportunities-2>
 - Synthesis of natural capital and valuation outcomes Alistair (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk)
<https://sefari.scot/research/projects/synthesis-of-natural-capital-and-valuation-outcomes>
- Understanding the value of Scotland's agricultural soil natural capital (alistair.mcvittie@sruc.ac.uk)
<https://sefari.scot/research/projects/understanding-the-value-of-scotland%E2%80%99s-agricultural-soil-natural-capital>

Some recent updates and highlights

- Simone Martino's project (JHI-D5-1) has just released an analytical framework proposing how a mix of methods could be used to investigate, represent and work with monetary and non-monetary values to support landscape-scale decision-making. [Please contact Simone to access or check back when webpage restored]
- Mike Rivington's project (JHI-D5-2) has produced quite sobering outputs showing how the interacting effects of climate change on Scotland's land and natural capital. [2 page summary at <https://www.hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/2-page-Executive-Summary-climate-trends-projections-extremes-implications-for-Natural-Capital-and-Policy-12-7-23.pdf>] Scenario-planning workshops with stakeholders have highlighted new risks to natural capital arising from climate change, especially (but not only) increasing probability and severity of wildfires.
- Kerry Waylen's project (JHI-D5-3) has carried out a survey of perceptions of natural capital and related issues and tools within Scottish Government: early results suggest that there is a desire to do more to embed nature and sustainability considerations into policy development, but a lack of familiarity with existing natural tools that might help. Early results and other articles are presented in our recent newsletter (https://www.hutton.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/2024/05/24_03_20_JHI-D5-3Newsletter_March2024final.pdf)

Contact Kerry.Waylen@hutton.ac.uk for further details about the Natural Capital Topic.

Nitrogen impacts in natural ecosystems

Lead PI: **Andrea Britton** (andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve understanding of the impacts of nitrogen deposition on Scottish natural ecosystems in the context of a changing climate, providing evidence on how natural ecosystems are changing, what is driving this change and how best to manage and protect them.

Current specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Nitrogen and climate impacts on above and below ground biodiversity in alpine ecosystems

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

We are revisiting long term vegetation plots 50 years after the first sampling to examine how nitrogen and climate change are affecting plant and soil biodiversity in alpine habitats. During summer 2023, 102 locations across Scotland were revisited and another 100 locations will be visited in summer 2024. Vegetation composition is recorded, and moss and soil samples are being collected for chemical analysis and DNA analysis of soil biodiversity.

2. Nitrogen and climate impacts on woodland ectomycorrhizal communities

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

Using data from the National Biodiversity Network and new data collected from birch, oak and pine forests across Scotland, we are investigating how nitrogen deposition and climate affect woodland fungal communities. New fungal community data has been generated from soil samples collected under pine, oak and birch woodlands in 2022 and 2023, with final sample collection in September 2024. Data collected in 2022 and 2023 are already expanding our geographic and taxonomic coverage, with many new taxa to the UK and Scotland recorded, increasing our evidence base and knowledge of natural capital.

3. Impacts of nitrogen climate interactions on ecosystem function

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

Using long-term (20+ years) experimental plots in alpine heath we are investigating how warming, nitrogen additions and burning affect carbon and nutrient stocks, nutrient cycling and above and belowground biodiversity. Results show that although the added nitrogen is no longer present in the vegetation 12 years after additions ceased, added nitrogen is still present in the organic soil horizon. Nitrogen addition also appears to have long term effects on vegetation chemistry through reductions in phosphorus content. In terms of biodiversity, while nitrogen addition no longer had any effect on plant community composition it did have lasting effects on the soil fungal community. Strong effects of warming and burning were also seen on both ecosystem biogeochemistry and soil biodiversity. However, ecosystem carbon stocks did not show any detectable responses to the treatments. The results of this study can also be used to demonstrate the effectiveness of different ecosystem metrics as indicators of long-term nitrogen impacts.

4. Modelling of nitrogen climate interactions

Contact: mike.rivington@hutton.ac.uk

Starting in 2025, we will be using data gained from all studies to model risks to Scottish ecosystems from interactive impacts of nitrogen deposition and climate change.

5. Experimental trial of nitrogen mitigation methods and indicators

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

We are examining the potential benefits of restoration in mitigating the impacts of nitrogen deposition on peatlands. Working with PeatlandACTION, paired restored and unrestored sites have been identified along a nitrogen deposition gradient. Methodologies for measurements of biogeochemical and biodiversity indicators of N impacts were trialed during summer 2023 and summer 2024 sampling will be extended across Scotland.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Nitrogen and climate: a review of the interactive effects of nitrogen deposition and climate change on Scottish semi-natural vegetation.](#)
- [Nitrogen mitigation: a review of nitrogen deposition impacts and mitigation potential in Scottish semi-natural ecosystems.](#)
- Further information and project updates are available from: www.hutton.ac.uk/NINE

People and Nature

Lead PI: **Katherine (Kate) Irvine** (kate.irvine@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Identify and evaluate interventions, approaches and processes to facilitate the transformative change of how Scotland's biodiversity is framed, valued, managed and governed, and how to harness and more equitably distributed the associated benefits.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

For further information on any of the objectives below please contact Kate.Irvine@hutton.ac.uk

- 1. Nature and Economy:** Explore nature-economy relations and the implications of different framings for managing nature.

Analysis of interviews with stakeholders about perceptions of nature-economy relations completed and draft report being developed. Presentation of preliminary findings to stakeholders in January 2024.
- 2. Enabling inclusivity in biodiversity narratives:** Identify narrative and approaches which are usually outside of biodiversity research, and develop and evaluate audio-visual and interactive narrative tools and techniques to better enable their productive engagement for transformative change.

Archival cultural, mapping, and ecological data identified, and permission secured for digital platform inclusion. Fieldwork commenced for continued identification of biodiversity narratives for platform.
- 3. Enabling transformative biodiversity research and change:** Examine how novel management interventions and transformative research can enable more diverse, sustainable and just futures.

Fieldwork exploring peer-to-peer knowledge transfer project as an intervention to foster collaborative and landscape scale management completed. Analysis underway.
- 4. Values:** To understand the different societal, economic and biological values associated with biodiversity within nature conservation and farming practices, and how these values may be leveraged and changed with transformative research.
Research protocol developed and preliminary literature review commenced for study to investigate the feasibility and acceptability of a nature-based intervention for transformative value change.
- 5. Harnessing Green / Blue Infrastructure for people and nature:** Focuses on how to assess green-blue infrastructure for multiple benefits through investigating the impact of different types of interventions.

Analysis of interviews about impact of participation in nature-engagement programmes completed and draft report submitted. Quality of urban life and place-based nature interventions survey finalised. Ethics application under development.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project website: <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/people-and-nature>

Identifying the causes of biodiversity change with specific references to the IPBES drivers

Lead PI: **Robin Pakeman** (robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to identify how the "IPBES drivers", specifically climate change, land use change, pollution and invasive species, affect key parts of Scotland's biodiversity.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

- 1. Global change impacts on sustainable upland land use** Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk
We have been developing methods to assess the spread of trees and shrubs into the experimental plots to set a baseline as the local deer management group are about to substantially reduce numbers. The paper assessing the impact of vegetation structure of meadow pipit territory size has been submitted. It appears territory sizes are larger where the vegetation is denser.
- 2. Collective landscape management of farmland biodiversity** Contact: graham.begg@hutton.ac.uk
The Buchan Farmer Cluster has been operating since 2021 and has updated its biodiversity friendly activities to include trials on an RSPB bird and butterfly seed mix plus initial trials of minimum tillage. Biodiversity monitoring for 2024 is underway. Engagement with cluster stakeholders is exploring the potential for increasing the adoption of the cluster approach for landscape scale management.
- 3. Using long-term aphid monitoring data to assess drivers of biodiversity change** Contact: ali.karley@hutton.ac.uk
An initial analysis of trends in aphid diversity and abundance over 70 years of data collected from the Dundee suction trap has highlighted shifts in aphid species composition during certain decades and changes in within-year seasonal composition. Land use and pesticide use data have been assessed for their utility as explanatory variables for the next stage of the analysis.
- 4. Using Scotland's Caledonian forest as a model system to assess impacts of major climate drivers** Contact: alison.hester@hutton.ac.uk, jenni.sockan@hutton.ac.uk
Our "future drought scenarios" experiment on native Scots pine saplings is ongoing. We have now completed 2 years of drought treatments and are continuing to monitor bud burst, growth and survival of young pines in each treatment group.
- 5. Assessing potential effect of chemical pollution on the wild Scottish salmon** Contact: zulin.zhang@hutton.ac.uk
The water and salmon samples from River Dee have been collected for the analysis of endocrine disrupting compounds. The River Dee Trust have agreed to help sampling particularly for the salmon samples collection. Sampling campaign for the EDCs monitoring in the water and salmon from River Dee will continue into years 3 and year 4.
- 6. Improved technology to track invasive non-native pathogens and their effects on ecosystems** Contact: david.cooke@hutton.ac.uk
Amplification of the new broad oomycete marker and corresponding synthetic barcode controls has been completed and will be sequenced in May. Existing sequence and meta-data back to 2018 will be uploaded to the European Nucleotide Archive in line with Open Science objectives.
- 7. Impact Assessment of Invasive Non-Native Species** Contact: michaela.roberts@hutton.ac.uk; ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk
A report reviewing the potential costs and impacts of INNS on moorlands and heathlands has been published. This included an assessment of the impact of the loss of key plant species in these habitats due to plant pests and pathogens.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Karley, A.J. (2024) 'Response of potato aphids to biotic and abiotic stress: why diversity matters'. An invited talk at an international workshop: Pest control under drought - A new challenge to plant science on the horizon, held at the Instituto de Ciencias Biológicas, Universidad de Talca, Chile.
- Cooke, D.E.L., Randall, E., Keillor, B., Cock, P.J.A., Pritchard, L., Frederickson Matika, D. & Green S. (2024) A robust eDNA toolkit for exploring oomycete pathogens of plants and animals. Invited paper at Microbiology Society Annual Conference 2024 8-11 April 2024, Edinburgh, UK.
- Roberts, M. & Michell, R. (2024) Impacts and costs of invasive non-native species, including plant pests and pathogens, establishment in heath and moorland habitats. Report to Scottish Government [10.5281/zenodo.11058291](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11058291)

Scotland's biodiversity: People, data and monitoring

Lead PI: **Jenni Stockan** (jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

The aim of this project is to help protect Scotland's share of global biodiversity by optimising people's skills, data, and technologies to ensure effective recording and monitoring techniques and data flows.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Creating a Scottish biodiversity inventory

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We are compiling data on the extant taxa in Scotland using post 1950 data and their taxonomic backbone from the NBN Atlas as the basis for records. Comparisons with the 1997 last full inventory of Scottish biodiversity are continuing, but there is still a large discrepancy between this past estimate and current taxon richness. Verification of records (identification, locality, date) is proving challenging for some taxon groups. Specialist datasets (in particular insects) are being mined for additional species records.

2. Improved reporting

Contact: robin.pakeman@hutton.ac.uk

The paper assessing the impact of different weighting methods to allocate species trends to habitats to derive habitat level trends has been submitted. We are currently exploring with State of Nature partners the possibility of publishing a data paper. This would create an accessible record of trend information that could be further analysed by the scientific community.

3. Oceanic-alpine soil biodiversity

Contact: andrea.britton@hutton.ac.uk

The Mountain Heights, Hidden Depths citizen science project aims to explore and map alpine soil biodiversity across 270 of Scotland's Munros. The project was launched in June 2023 and >400 volunteers signed up to take part. Each of the Munros has been 'adopted' by a volunteer who has been sent an information and sampling pack with guidance on where and how to collect samples and return them for analysis. Sampling is taking place during June-September in 2023 and 2024. After the first summer we had received samples from 170 Munros and we aim to sample the remaining 100 Munros during 2024. DNA has now been extracted from the 510 samples we have received so far (3 per Munro) and we have just received the first sequence data. Measurements of soil pH and carbon and nitrogen content have also been made and photographs of each sample point have been used to classify the samples according to vegetation type.

4. Monitoring approaches for outcomes focused interventions

Contact: cathy.hawes@hutton.ac.uk

A handbook of biodiversity and soil health monitoring protocols has been produced, based on tried and tested methods applied at the Centre for Sustainable Cropping long-term experimental platform and East of Scotland Farm Network, adapted for use by non-experts interested in assessing change in key indicators of biodiversity and soil properties. Further methods are now being assessed to extend the existing set of measurements to include biodiversity-driven measures of soil function (litter decomposition by soil organisms).

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Walton, P et al. (2023) State of Nature Scotland 2023. The State of Nature Partnership. <https://stateofnature.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/TP26056-SoN-Scotland-summary-report-v5-1.pdf.pagespeed.ce.ElP-TYaoGQ.pdf>

Habitat management and restoration

Lead PI: **Andy Taylor** (Andy.Taylor@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To gain biodiversity in moorland and woodland habitats through evidence-based land management and restoration to maximise benefits to society.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1 How can public and private sector investors, at low risk, restore woodland habitats for the most multiple benefits to society in addition to increasing natural carbon capture and biodiversity, and what land is available for this?

Contact: matt.hare@hutton.ac.uk

Our work is focused on developing the evidence base, through mapping, community consultation and simulation, on the flow of multiple benefits to society and communities (as well as risks related to climate change and investor behaviour) associated with woodland habitat expansion in Scotland. We are doing this using an interdisciplinary approach that combines geo-spatial data analysis, participatory community-based assessment and socio-biophysical integrated modelling. We have produced our first set of mapping results covering 30+ years of woodland expansion activities in Scotland and are currently preparing our summer field work in Edinburgh in order to elicit local communities' perspectives on the benefits and risks flowing from urban woodland creation. Finally, an empirically-derived set of investor archetypes, including their potential behaviours, is being developed, which will be used to add a realistic investor behaviour component to our socio-biophysical modelling. The resulting simulation tool will allow the assessment of future woodland expansion strategies across Scotland in terms of maximising benefit flows and mitigating risks, at different scales.

2 What is the impact of Muirburn on nature and how does this impact compare to mechanical removal of vegetation?

Contact: stuart.smith@hutton.ac.uk

For our desk-based research, after the first round of reviews we are revising our paper analysing the spatial overlap between muirburn and wildfires across moorland habitats in Scotland. The main finding being limited spatial overlap between these fire events. For our field experiments at Glensaugh and Abernethy, all fieldwork and labwork processing is now complete with collection of temperature data loggers and lolly sticks (medium decomposition proxies) at the end of the winter. Preliminary analysis of soil nutrient probes, suggest no significant difference in soil available nutrients between treatments, including between control, (mechanical removal) and burning. We are currently analysing remaining plant-soil functional data from the treatments (biomass removed, decomposition proxies and soil temperature).

3 How do our ancient woodlands function and how successful is woodland restoration?

Contact: andy.taylor@hutton.ac.uk

We are assessing the impact of PAWS creation with conifers on the soil functional biodiversity in Atlantic Oak woodland and the subsequent changes associated with restoration management. We established a field study site at Glen Creran in collaboration with FLS, where we sampled 42 plots arrayed across 6 different management areas. Data on C and nutrient cycling and taxonomic and functional biodiversity were collected using nutrient probes coupled with decomposition assays, and sequence metabarcoding. Soil biodiversity shows strong differences among each of the management areas and this is reflected in the rates of nutrient and C cycling. We are currently in the process of selecting new PAWS restoration sites for another in depth field analysis.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Project website <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/habitat-management-and-restoration>

Protected areas to tackle biodiversity loss now, and for the future

Lead PI: **Ruth Mitchell** (ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To improve our understanding of how to design effective protected area networks against a backdrop of rapid environmental change and how to measure the success of protected areas.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

- 1. Can applying a seascape approach to marine protection benefit biodiversity protection and improve fishery sustainability?** Contact: neil.burns@sruc.ac.uk
Our work in 2023 continues to develop understanding of the mosaic of habitats required to properly protect marine fish biodiversity. Specifically, we are building knowledge on which habitat combinations are important for survival and growth of juvenile fish, including cod, haddock and whiting. The data collected from Loch Eriboll and Little Loch Broom now amounts to over 700 Stereo Baited Remote Underwater Video (SBRUV) camera deployments and has been used to build seabed habitat maps (paper in review). The camera deployments collecting data on fish abundances are also informing understanding of elasmobranch ecology (paper in prep) and supplementing data for two PhD projects.
- 2. How can protected areas ensure that threatened genetic diversity is safeguarded?** Contact: jenni.stockan@hutton.ac.uk
Using our datasets from the early years of our pine progeny-provenance trial we are looking at trait differences of Scots pines grown in different nursery environments and the carryover effects from nursery to plantation (2 papers in prep). These results are highlighting the importance of the early environment for trees. Genotyping of all trees in our trial has been completed and analysis is underway. In 2024 we will be working with Forest Research to undertake surveys of fungal pathogens at our trial sites to better understand tree susceptibility and resilience.
- 3. Can we identify refugia for species which are unlikely to disperse quickly in the face of a changing climate?** Contact: c.ellis@rbge.ac.uk
The first stage of datalogging is now complete, with data for microhabitats in each of the three NNRs, provided for a summer period, a winter period, and an entire year (= 18 months in total). This data is now being analysed, aiming towards a submitted publication by the end of 2024. Concomitantly, the Rainforest Research Working Group of the Alliance for Scotland's rainforest has run a prioritization of knowledge gaps, highlighting, for example: "How variable are UK rainforest microclimates?" and "Assess rainforest microclimates to inform spatial planning" the results of this project will directly inform these stakeholder evidence needs.
- 4. How do we measure the success of our protected areas?**
Contact: ruth.mitchell@hutton.ac.uk
Initial analysis has been completed on two long-term vegetation data sets from 1970's-2000's studying changes in vegetation inside and outside protected areas, across a range of habitats within Scotland. The results show that the dynamics of vegetation change are similar within and outside protected areas. Further work will explore if there are differences in the species composition changes. In addition, we have working with NatureScot to test an approach to Ecosystem Health monitoring in woodlands as part of a revision of the monitoring of protected areas.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- Website: <https://sefari.scot/research/projects/protected-areas-to-tackle-biodiversity-loss-now-and-for-the-future>
- [Does protected area status prevent biodiversity decline in plant communities?](#) Ruth Mitchell & Jackie Potts (2024) SEFARI case study

Assessing the impact of changing migratory patterns, population size and diversity of greylag geese on livestock and public health

Lead PI: **Eleanor Watson** (eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

To investigate the microbial risks associated with rapidly expanded resident and migratory greylag goose populations on Orkney, and assess economic, conservation and social impacts.

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

1. Investigate transmission of *Cryptosporidium parvum*, *Campylobacter* and antimicrobial resistance between geese, calves and cattle and the wider environment

Contacts: clare.hamilton@moredun.ac.uk (*Cryptosporidium*), eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk (*Campylobacter*) and nuno.silva@moredun.ac.uk (antimicrobial resistance)

Goose faecal samples have been collected during the wintering season (November 2022) and goose, cattle, calf and environmental samples have been collected during pre-and post-turnout of calves to pasture (April and June 2023).

All samples have been processed to isolate *Campylobacter* and *Cryptosporidium* and molecular approaches will be used for speciation of both pathogens. DNA sequencing data will be generated to identify pathogen genotypes, which will be used to assess likelihood of transmission between cattle, calves and geese during years 3-5.

Methods to extract bacterial DNA from archived faecal samples for detection of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) are currently being appraised. qPCR array technology will be used to identify ARGs within samples in years 3-4, and allow carriage of ARGs by geese, cattle and calves to be compared.

2. Development of molecular tools to genotype geese Contact: keith.ballingall@moredun.ac.uk

Additional goose faecal samples from breeding sites in Iceland have been shipped and archived. Methods to extract goose DNA from faeces have been assessed and optimised and DNA of sufficient quality and quantity has successfully been extracted for molecular analysis. Methods to amplify loci of interest for goose genotyping have been optimised for DNA sequenced analysis. Samples from Barnacle geese have also been collected through a collaboration with NatureScot and the University of Edinburgh to progress the development of these molecular methods to support avian flu surveillance.

3. Engage with stakeholder groups to inform project progression, assess impact of findings and highlight successful approaches for related studies

Contact: eleanor.watson@moredun.ac.uk and beth.wells@moredun.ac.uk

A summary document containing results from the migratory sampling time period has been prepared and a stakeholder event in Orkney is currently being organised.

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [A panel of goose and cattle *Campylobacter* isolates have been submitted for genome sequencing and analysis through the Food Standards Agency-led Pathogen Surveillance in Agriculture, Food and Environment \(PATH-SAFE\) programme.](#)
- [Funding secured from the UK – Iceland Arctic Science Partnership Scheme to visit field locations in Iceland, including greylag geese breeding sites, to pilot ecosystem sampling using eDNA approaches.](#)

Seeking multiple benefits from natural carbon stores in the uplands

Lead PI: **Davy McCracken** (davy.mccracken@sruc.ac.uk)

Overall project aim:

Explore the relationship between carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to detect synergies and trade-offs and identify land management practices that optimise the benefits derived

Specific objectives and summary of recent work

Our work is focused on SRUC's Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms where we are focusing on carbon storage (in the soil, and vegetation), biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation.

- 1. Ground-truth existing maps of carbon storage potential and flood mitigation using on the ground surveys and environmental sensors to monitor rainfall and water flow, and expand the spatial coverage of these maps to include all predominant habitats on the estate.**

All progressing on track.

- 2. Supplement existing biodiversity datasets, through the collection of new biodiversity data to expand spatial coverage to cover all predominant habitats present on the farm, and implement innovative approaches to monitor biodiversity (e.g., acoustic sensors and camera traps)**

Audiomoth acoustic loggers and camera traps have been deployed on lowland and upland sites for the second year. Work is ongoing to develop a guidance document for the use of Audiomoth loggers for detecting bird occurrence, with the aim of helping users identify and remove false positives.

- 3. Trial scorecards developed under NatureScot's project Piloting an Outcomes Based Approach (POBAS) in Scotland and the NatureScot Civtech Challenge Habitat Quality app to determine how effective proposed scorecards are as indicators of wider biodiversity**

Liaison with NatureScot ongoing, with one online and one in-person meeting held at the farms in summer 2023 to initiate further testing of their Habitat Quality App and discuss issues they have identified with upland mosaics.

- 4. Quantify the relationships between metrics relating to carbon storage, biodiversity conservation and flood mitigation to identify synergies and trade-offs between these key ecosystem services, and identify land management practices that optimise these multiple benefits**

To complete in Year 4

- 5. Utilise data from Kirkton and Auchtertyre farms to create spatial models of carbon storage, biodiversity conservation potential and flood mitigation for part of the upper River Tay catchment, and collect additional data to ground-truth these at several sites, to test the scalability of findings generated during this study**

To complete in Year 5

Recent highlights or outputs:

- [Input continuing to discussions on how best to include biodiversity conditions on future agricultural support direct payments through participation in the Academic Advisory Panel advising the ARIOB process and the Programme Advisory Group advising on Scotland's Biodiversity Strategy.](#)
- [Members of Scottish Parliament's Rural Affairs & Environment Committee visited the farms in November 2023.](#)
- [An overview of the work was presented to attendees at a RESAS Strategic Research Programme Ecosystem & Land Use Stakeholder Engagement Group \[ELSEG\] meeting in January 2024.](#)

ELPEG Policy Update

Biodiversity Policy

The 'Tackling the nature emergency: Consultation on Scotland's Strategic Framework for Biodiversity' closed at the end of last year. The consultation outlined:

- The first 5 year delivery plan for the Scottish Biodiversity Strategy;
- Proposed policy frameworks for nature networks and 30x30;
- Proposals for how statutory targets will be selected and set in the natural environment and;
- Proposals to update the National Parks legislation

These work areas are all continuing to develop post-consultation.

A key recommendation of the research into the use of biodiversity in metrics in Scotland that was published last year was to develop a common framework for the use of site level biodiversity metrics in Scotland.

Taking these recommendations, a good practice guidance document to help policy makers select suitable biodiversity metrics has been developed. The guidance is due for publication in early summer 2024.

Wildlife Management

The Wildlife Management and Muirburn (Scotland) Act 2024 was passed by Parliament in March this year and has recently received royal assent. The Bill: bans the use of snares in Scotland, bans the use, supply and possession of glue traps to catch rodents, gives greater powers to the Scottish SPCA to tackle wildlife crime, introduces a new a new licensing framework for grouse shooting and strictly regulates and restricts the practice of muirburn. More detail on the Act can be found [here](#) and the legislation can be found [here](#).

Agricultural Reform

The Agriculture and Rural Communities (Scotland) Bill was introduced to Parliament on 28th September 2023 and the general principles of the Bill were unanimously agreed following the Stage 1 debate on 27th March 2024. The Bill provides Scotland with a future framework which will support farmers and crofters to meet more of our food needs sustainably and to farm and croft with nature, and will assist in efforts to meet our climate change targets.

The agricultural reform programme to support delivery of the Vision for Agriculture continues to develop through a co-production approach. The new payments framework will be split into four tiers: Basic, Enhanced, Elective and Complimentary.

Recent developments within the programme have seen the confirmation of changes to take place from 2025, these include:

- New conditions under cross compliance related to a new wetland and peatland standard within GAEC 6. This will prohibit new drainage and maintenance of existing drainage systems that cause further peatland drying, and activities that cause damage to peatland vegetation exposing the soil.
- The introduction of Whole Farm Plans as part of basic payments will see farmers and crofters conducting plans and audits relevant to their business. At least two activities from: carbon audit, biodiversity audit, soil analysis, animal health and welfare plan and Integrated Pest Management Plan will be required.

More detail can be found on the Agricultural Reform Route Map [here](#).

Relevant Scottish Government funded work outside the SRP

The following commissioned reports have been published that are relevant to ELPEG:

Grazing and biodiversity:

A group from JHI and SRUC produced a Q and A style briefing report on the impacts of grazing (both domestic and wild) on biodiversity through the RESAS call down process. This work has been used to inform policy development on land reform.

British Ecological Society (BES) Fellows:

Two early career policy fellowships funded by RESAS and administered by the BES have just completed. Robert Patchett (University of St Andrews) assessed how the measures published in the agricultural reform route map impact biodiversity. A key part of this work was to review the recently published [DEFRA QEIA](#) for use in Scotland. James Robinson (University of Edinburgh) used two measures from the ARP route map as case studies to identify support needs for farmers in Scotland during the transition towards regenerative arable agriculture. Both reports from these projects will soon be published on the BES website.

CxC ARP data and metrics project:

A CxC project being undertaken by JHI on Understanding metrics for effective environmental measures under the Agricultural Reform Programme for Scotland will be soon to complete. Taking each of the proposed measures in the ARP route map, the project reviews and makes recommendations on suitable metrics for assessing environmental outcomes associated with each measure.